

**ECONOMIC COOPERATION BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND
EUROPEAN UNION**

Siddikjon Gafurov

Student of the Tashkent State

University of Economics

Phone: +998940044439

Email: siddikjan.tsue@gmail.com

Abstract: In the last two decades, economic cooperation between Uzbekistan and European Union (EU) has been increasing and plays a crucial role in the foreign economic policies of Uzbekistan. This study analyzes mutual benefits in enhanced economic cooperation, increased market access, investment opportunities and collaborative initiatives. Examining the present-day trends in trade, the article delves into key sectors fostering this cooperation, such as energy, technology, and infrastructure development of Uzbekistan with European countries. This article also aims to discuss Uzbekistan's membership in Generalized System of Preferences Plus (GSP+) and its sustainable economic benefits for Uzbekistan. It also addresses the challenges faced in the last years because of the conflict between Russia and Ukraine and potential opportunities for further collaboration.

Key words: European Union, Economic cooperation, FDI, GDP, export, import, foreign trade turnover, Uzbekistan, GSP+, trade.

Introduction

Relations between the European Union and the Republic of Uzbekistan have been developing steadily since its independence in 1991. EU relations with Uzbekistan are embedded in the regularly reviewed EU and Central Asia Strategy for a New Partnership, which outlines the overall cooperation objectives, policy responses and priority fields for the EU's engagement in Central Asia (EU-Uzbekistan relations, 2018).

The European Union, which unites 27 countries, ranks third after China and India in terms of population, and ranks seventh in the world in terms of land area, has a significant role in Uzbekistan's foreign policy (Olimjonovna, 2020). Multilateral and bilateral relations with the European Union organization and its member states are one of the main directions of our country's foreign policy (Olimjonovna, 2020).

The economic cooperation between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the EU dates back to 1996 when the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement (PCA) was signed by both parties and in 1999 it came into force¹. The agreement promotes economic cooperation and trade liberalization between Uzbekistan and the EU. It includes provisions for the gradual integration of Uzbekistan into the world economy. The PCA promotes trade by addressing issues such as market access, trade barriers, and the harmonization of trade-related standards. Under the existing Partnership and Cooperation Agreement (PCA), the EU and Uzbekistan grant each other most-favored-nation treatment concerning:

- Customs duties and charges applied to imports and exports;
- Direct and indirect taxes applied to imported goods;
- Rules relating to the sale, purchase, transport, distribution and use of goods on the domestic market.

The EU is also providing technical assistance for Uzbekistan's application to accede to the World Trade Organization (WTO).

Furthermore, the location of Uzbekistan in Central Asia can be used to connect trade routes in Asia and Europe. Over the past few years, the country has been actively seeking to diversify its economy and develop trade. From April 10, 2021, the European Union (EU) system of special preferences for sustainable development and effective governance (GSP+) came into force, in which Uzbekistan was accepted as a beneficiary country under the Generalized Scheme of Preferences (GSP) (Uzbekistan joins EU's GSP+ arrangement, 2021). It provides a strong incentive for investors and

¹ [The European Union and Uzbekistan | EEAS \(europa.eu\)](https://eeas.europa.eu/)

representatives of the private sector from EU countries to implement promising projects in Uzbekistan, and also creates a solid foundation for diversification and rapid development of mutual trade and economic relations between Uzbekistan and EU countries.

It is undeniable that international trade plays a significant role in economic growth and development of developing nations. It helps also fights against poverty and international trade has the potential to influence positively to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Uzbekistan. Economic cooperation between EU and Uzbekistan has several potential benefits, increased economic relations with European countries have led to increased trade, investment, and technology transfers. For example, statistical data indicates that in just 10 months of 2023, the volume of mutual trade increased by 36% compared to the same period last year and amounted to \$4.8 billion. The growth in exports of products from Uzbekistan to EU countries was especially noted; since 2021, the figure has increased 1.5 times – to \$794.6 million at the end of 2022 (kun.uz, 2023).

Market access to the larger and increasing markets of European countries have opened new opportunities for Uzbek exporters. Uzbekistan has enjoyed its competitive advantages in sectors such as agriculture, textiles and minerals to tap into these markets. In addition to this, Uzbekistan has attracted foreign direct investment (FDI) from European countries, which have also been major sources of FDI. This has helped to stimulate economic growth, create job opportunities, and contribute infrastructure and industries.

Literature review

The economic cooperation of Uzbekistan with European Union has been the subject of scholarly research and analysis. This literature review aims to provide an overview of existing studies and insights on the topic. Several studies have highlighted the potential benefits of economic relations of Uzbekistan with EU in the long-term economic growth of Uzbekistan. According to (Yuldasheva, 2022) despite the fact that the area (as well as Uzbekistan itself) has been

neglected for a long time, the EU has surprisingly become the region's top trading partner in 2019, accounting for 24,1 percent of total trade. They emphasize Uzbekistan's trade agreements with EU and importance of some European countries' economic, scientific, technical, and cultural collaborations with Uzbekistan.

The scholarly works emphasize the significance of economic integration in promoting trade, investment, and economic ties between Uzbekistan and nations in Europe. (Madina Yuldasheva, 2022) underscore the positive outcomes that can arise from expanding international contacts and establishing stronger economic ties. The writers explore the potential advantages of heightened trade and investment activities, underscoring the prospects for shared growth and progress.

Furthermore, the literature has explored potential geopolitical implications of the war between Russia and Ukraine for the relations of Uzbekistan with EU. (Makhmudov, 2023) argues the ongoing Ukrainian conflict has reverberated across the global landscape, considerably altering the dynamics of international relations. Within this context, the relationship between the European Union and Uzbekistan has undergone a noticeable transformation, marking a pivotal shift in their interactions.

Methodology

The research methodology encompasses the gathering of relevant data from diverse sources, a thorough literature review to analyze existing studies, the utilization of statistical methods to analyze the data, a comparative analysis involving economic cooperation of Uzbekistan with EU, the construction of scenarios to simulate outcomes, and a policy analysis. The primary objective of this research is to offer insights into the economic possibilities associated with Uzbekistan's economic relations with European countries, taking into account factors such as trade patterns, investment flows, sector-specific ramifications, and policy implications. The study acknowledges its constraints and suggests potential areas for future research to attain a more holistic understanding of the subject.

Data Analysis

According to (Statistics Agency under the president of the republic of Uzbekistan, 2023) as a result of the measures implemented in the republic in recent years to stimulate exports, optimize imports and, in general, to ensure a balanced foreign trade, in January-November 2023 the foreign trade turnover (FTT) in the country amounted to 57.3 billion US dollars and increased compared to the same period of last year, by 11.9 billion US dollars, or by 26.2%. Of the total FTT volume, exports amounted to 23 204.3 million US dollars (an increase of 30.6% was noted by January-November 2023), and imports amounted to 34 105.8 million US dollars (an increase of 23.3%). As a result, the balance of foreign trade turnover amounted to a negative balance of -10 901.5 million US dollars (Statistics Agency under the president of the republic of Uzbekistan, 2023).

Table 1

The dynamics of large EU partner countries in foreign trade turnover of the Republic of Uzbekistan: (for January-November, million US dollars)

Countries	2021 (million USD)	2022 (million USD)	2023 (million USD)
Germany	675.4	948.6	962.4
Export	60.8	92.1	72.0
Import	614.6	856.5	890.4
France	257.6	311.4	831.7
Export	20.1	69.5	385.9
Import	237.5	241.9	445.8
Lithuania	445.5	449.3	566.8
Export	59.0	83.3	129.1
Import	396.5	366.0	437.7
Italy	393.5	348.2	468.4
Export	36.4	51.2	69.0
Import	357.1	297.0	399.4

Poland	211.7	315.8	369.6
Export	77.7	126.7	85.0
Import	134.0	189.1	284.6

Source: ITC (International Trade Centre) calculations based on The State Committee of Republic of Uzbekistan on statistics.

From this table we can see that the total amount of trade between Uzbekistan and European countries has been increasing gradually since 2021.

Export structure: Uzbekistan is paying great attention to develop agriculture and horticulture and exporting mainly agricultural products mainly: grape, onion, dried prunes, dried grapes, tomato, apricot to European countries. Furthermore, the increase in textile exports can be seen as a result of reforms undertaken to produce finished goods instead of raw cotton and create added value. Uzbekistan enjoys increased trade volume of textile products such as: finished textile products, yarn, knitted fabric and socks to EU.

However, when it comes to the **import structure** of the republic of Uzbekistan from European countries: according to (Statistics Agency under the president of the republic of Uzbekistan, 2023) the main share in its structure is occupied by machinery and transport equipment (38.8%), industrial goods (16.8%), as well as chemicals and similar products (13.0%).

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) plays a pivotal role in the development of a country, contributing to various aspects of its economic and social progress of Uzbekistan. FDI brings in significant capital from foreign investors, which can be crucial for financing various development projects, such as infrastructure, technology upgrades, and industrial expansion in Uzbekistan. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) from the European Union (EU) to Uzbekistan holds significant importance for the economic development and growth of Uzbekistan.

In terms of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) a second table below by (Investment Promotion Agency under the former Ministry of Investments and Foreign Trade of Uzbekistan, 2021) shows main 5 top investing countries in 2021. While China, Russia

and Turkey are three biggest investing countries, European country; Germany places at the fourth in terms of FDI.

Table 2

Main investing countries in Uzbekistan

Main investing countries in Uzbekistan

Year: 2021

Rank	Country	Direct investment (USD, stock)	Share	Variation (stock)	Inflows over past year (USD)
1	China	2.2 billion USD		+/- ...%	
2	Russia	2.1 billion USD		+/- ...%	
3	Türkiye	1.18 billion USD		+/- ...%	
4	Germany	800.7 million USD		+/- ...%	
5	Republic of Korea	137.4 million USD		+/- ...%	

Source: Investment Promotion Agency under the former Ministry of Investments and Foreign Trade of Uzbekistan,(data only available for 2021 and for top 5 investing countries)

Results

The analysis of the increased economic cooperation of Uzbekistan with European countries reveals both potential benefits and challenges.

Benefits:

•**International trade:** According to (Investment Promotion Agency under the former Ministry of Investments and Foreign Trade of Uzbekistan, 2021)in January-September of 2022, mutual trade between Uzbekistan and EU member states increased by almost 15% compared to the same period last year and reached \$3.1 billion, which became possible due to Uzbekistan obtaining the status of a GSP+ beneficiary.

•**Foreign Direct Investment:** Uzbekistan can attract more foreign direct investment from EU countries, which stimulates economic growth and infrastructure development of the country.

•**Market Access:** Increased economic cooperation can provide Uzbekistan with access to the large and growing markets of EU countries, creating new export opportunities for sectors, especially agriculture, where Uzbekistan has a competitive advantage.

Challenges:

•**Economic Diversification:** Uzbekistan needs to diversify its economy to align with the preferences and requirements of the EU members. Uzbekistan's heavy reliance on sectors such as agriculture sector and natural resources may need to be addressed to enhance its competitiveness.

•**Trade Imbalances:** Imbalances may even arise if Uzbekistan's exports do not align with the demands of the EU countries, potentially leading to trade deficits (Madina Yuldasheva, 2022).

•**Competition:** Trading with the EU countries means Uzbekistan should have to compete with existing EU member states in certain sectors, requiring adjustments in export strategies and trade policies.

The findings of the study emphasize the possible prospects for increased trade, investment, and market entry for Uzbekistan within the EU framework. However, there are challenges that need to be addressed, such as the need for economic diversification, the management of trade imbalances, and the need to adapt to competition with existing European countries. Policymakers should carefully consider these aspects when evaluating the potential benefits and challenges of Uzbekistan's economic cooperation with the EU.

Discussion

The examination of Uzbekistan's economic collaboration with EU nations entails evaluating both identified advantages and challenges, along with broader implications and factors to be taken into account.

The prospective advantages of Uzbekistan's economic collaboration with the EU are noteworthy. Strengthened economic ties with EU members have the potential to result in heightened levels of trade, increased investment, and the transfer of

technology. Existing trade statistics underscore a substantial trade volume between Uzbekistan and EU nations, with Germany and France standing out as significant trade partners. This suggests the possibility of continued expansion and enhanced market access for Uzbek exports. Furthermore, attracting additional foreign direct investment from EU countries has the capacity to stimulate economic growth and contribute to infrastructure development in Uzbekistan.

Nevertheless, Uzbekistan faces several challenges that require attention. Economic diversification is paramount, given the heavy reliance on sectors like agriculture and natural resources in Uzbekistan's economy. Diversifying the economic landscape would not only bolster competitiveness but also align with the economic structures of EU countries. The risk of trade imbalances looms if Uzbekistan's exports are not in sync with the demands of EU nations, potentially resulting in trade deficits. Additionally, engaging in trade with European countries entails navigating competition from established members in specific sectors, necessitating adjustments in export strategies and trade policies.

Beyond the specific advantages and challenges outlined, there are broader considerations to take into account. Economic cooperation with the EU has the potential to elevate Uzbekistan's geopolitical influence and global standing, offering a platform for active participation in shaping global economic and political discussions. However, it's crucial to acknowledge that Uzbekistan is a relatively small developing country and lacks global recognition as a powerful economy. Therefore, additional research and analysis are imperative to comprehensively grasp the potential outcomes and provide valuable insights to policymakers and stakeholders.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the prospective economic collaboration between Uzbekistan and the European Union (EU) presents a nuanced landscape characterized by both promising opportunities and formidable challenges. Envisaging a partnership holds the potential for Uzbekistan to establish strengthened economic ties, gain increased market access, and unlock new investment opportunities, ultimately leading to a notable

upswing in trade volumes and the transfer of advanced technologies. However, these promising prospects are accompanied by challenges that necessitate careful consideration.

Foremost among these challenges is the imperative for Uzbekistan to diversify its economy. The current heavy reliance on sectors such as agriculture and natural resources demands a strategic shift to enhance overall competitiveness, aligning the nation's economic structure more closely with that of the EU countries. Trade imbalances emerge as another critical concern, emphasizing the importance of aligning Uzbekistan's export profile with the demands of EU nations to avert potential trade deficits.

Moreover, entering into economic collaboration with European counterparts requires Uzbekistan to adeptly navigate the competitive landscape. This involves making strategic adjustments to export strategies and trade policies to contend with existing members in specific sectors. While these challenges are significant, they represent integral aspects that must be addressed for a successful and mutually beneficial partnership.

Beyond these immediate considerations, there are broader geopolitical implications to contemplate. Successful economic cooperation with the EU could elevate Uzbekistan's global influence and standing, potentially providing the nation with a platform to actively participate in shaping global economic and political discussions. However, it is crucial to recognize that Uzbekistan, as a relatively small developing country, does not currently enjoy widespread global recognition as a powerful economic player.

In light of this, the actual ramifications of such a collaborative venture remain uncertain. Policymakers must exercise caution and undertake further research and analysis to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the potential outcomes. Informed decision-making and the formulation of effective policies hinge on a thorough exploration of the multifaceted aspects associated with Uzbekistan's economic relationship with the EU. As Uzbekistan navigates its path forward, it is

imperative to acknowledge the need for ongoing research to guide its evolving relationship with the EU and to ensure that any collaboration aligns with the nation's long-term economic and geopolitical objectives.

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